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Curriculum evaluation innovation in realizing superior madrasa in Ma Wahab Chasbullah Bahrul Ulum Tambakberas Jombang Indonesia

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Abstract

This research departs from the research context that the curriculum is the core of the field of education and influences all educational activities. With the development of education now, every educational institution must have innovation, especially in curriculum management, so that education will continue to develop and exist in facing the challenges of the times. Madrasah Aliyah Unggulan Wahab Chasbullah Bahrul 'Ulum Tambakberas also uses an integrated curriculum by combining the national curriculum with the pesantren curriculum. This cannot be separated from the innovation that continues to be carried out, especially in curriculum management.

The focus of this research is curriculum evaluation innovation in creating superior madrasa. This research uses a qualitative type of phenomenological approach, and the methods are interviews, observation and documentation. The data analysis used is data collection, data condensation, and conclusion. This research is expected to contribute to the study and development of theory in managing Islamic educational institutions, especially curriculum management innovation in creating superior madrasa.

The results of this study are curriculum evaluation innovations carried out by madrasah heads through evaluating educators/educational staff and students. The evaluation uses Google Forms, clinical supervision, continuous reviews with teachers, and madrasah self-evaluation (EDM). The assessment is carried out on students through tests and non-tests such as observations, tests, practices, and mentoring students who excel or have problems.

Keywords: Innovation; Curriculum Management; Leading Madrasah; Superior Madrasah; Madrasah Self-Evaluation

1. Introduction

Education always develops according to its era. Education in the digital age currently faces quite complex internal and external challenges. Internally, the problems faced include the educational components of teacher professionalism, curriculum and so on. In contrast, the external challenges faced relate to preparing education that can survive with challenges oriented towards the contemporary and future eras. (Wahid, 2021).

One way to build and develop madrasa is by extending the curriculum. The context of madrasa-based management must develop curriculum management. Therefore, the autonomy given to educational institutions must have innovation in their leadership so that they become superior madrasa. The curriculum can be set according to the needs of the vision and mission of the madrasah, of course, paying attention to the national education policies that have been established. (Nur Efendi, 2014)

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Curriculum innovation is a certainty that educational institutions must prepare to respond to the demands and needs of society. The curriculum as a reference material in the learning process must create and deliver the students expected by culture based on the needs of the times.

The word innovation in English is often translated as anything new or updated. In the popular scientific dictionary, it has been explained that what is meant by innovation is change that leads to renewal. (Widodo, 2002). Invention is carried out to achieve specific goals or to solve a particular problem. Discovery is the discovery of something that already exists, but no one knows its existence. Invention is the opposite of discovery, namely, true finding. That is the result of human creation itself. In Sa'ud's opinion, an innovation must be something that can solve the problems that occur. (Dadang Suhendar and Enas, 2019)

According to Anne Mai Walder, we are understanding curriculum innovation in the context of education. Curriculum innovation includes adjustment, improvement, development, study/pilot project, experiment, modernization, reform or renewal (adjustment, progress, growth, review/pilot project, experimentation, modernization, repair, or renewal). Innovation aspires to positive change, engenders performance, and a better way of doing it, and innovation involves changing intellectual approaches, attitudes, and behaviors. (Innovation wants positive change. Innovation gives birth to performance, and the best way, innovation requires a shift in intellectual approach, attitude and behaviour). (Walder, Anne Mai, 2014)

When assessing a curriculum implemented in educational institutions, it is necessary to evaluate it. A good evaluation is carried out comprehensively, covering all activities and curriculum components, judging from curriculum documents, implementation, results achieved, supporting facilities and curriculum implementers. (Nana Syaodih Sukmadinata, 2007)

Before discussing further curriculum evaluation, let us know the definition of curriculum evaluation. According to S Hamid Hasan, quoted by Rusman, evaluation is interpreted in various ways. This is because the scientific philosophy one adheres to influences the evaluation methodology and purpose. In turn, the meaning of the evaluation itself. There are many variations in the limits and implications of the evaluation given by experts, depending on the area of expertise and the field being evaluated. (Sukardi, 2014)

Meanwhile, McDonald argues, "Evaluation is the process of conceiving, obtaining and communicating information for the guidance of educational decision making with regard to a specified program." It can be understood that evaluation is the process of understanding, obtaining, and communicating information for decision-making guidelines. Educational decisions regarding specific programs. (John D McNeil, 1990)

Sukmadinata, stated that curriculum evaluation is essential in determining education policy in general and making decisions in particular curriculum. Curriculum evaluation is complex because of the many aspects that must be evaluated, the number of people involved, and the breadth of the curriculum that must be considered. In addition, curriculum evaluation is also related to the definition of the curriculum given, whether in the form of subject matter according to scientific disciplines or in a broad sense covering children's experiences inside and outside the classroom. (Sukiman, 2015)

Evaluating means assessing all activities to find indicators that cause success or failure in achieving goals so that they can be used as benchmarks or material for further study. Formulate alternative solutions that can improve existing weaknesses and improve the quality of success in the future. (Saefullah, 2012).

The curriculum development team at the educational unit level carries out curriculum development guided by applicable regulations and legislation, which are the reference for government policy in improving the quality of relevance and national education programs at all levels of education, including educational units developed and under the responsibility of the Ministry of Religion RI. (Syafaruddin and Amiruddin, 2017)

Evaluation is carried out to measure the achievements of an activity and see the extent to which the action can be implemented. A good evaluation is an evaluation that is formulated in detail so that it is genuinely known which activities can be carried out and which cannot. The objectives of implementing curriculum evaluation are as follows. (Zainal Arifin, 2012). The curriculum assessment program contains the following things. (Oemar Hamalik, 2008). 1) Determining the purpose of the assessment program. 2) Assessment of the assessment instrument. 3) Administrative assessment. 4) Data processing. 5) Analysis of interpretation. 6) Utilization of the results of the assessment. 7) Recording and reporting.

Norman and Schmidt stated several difficulties in implementing curriculum evaluation, namely as follows:

Difficulties in measuring the theoretical basis behind the curriculum will influence the evaluation of the curriculum. The insufficiency of theory in supporting the explanation of the intervention results of an evaluated curriculum will make the research (curriculum evaluation) not good.

The difficulty of conducting curriculum evaluation research using the randomization method can be caused by the small number of research subjects to be studied or perhaps only the institution itself doing it. If the intervention is used only at that institution, the question arises, "Is it possible to find a control group and randomization?" Apart from that, it is not possible to carry out blinded educational interventions. In academic research, especially curriculum evaluation research, difficulties were found in implementing blinded methods in educational interventions. By not being overwhelmed, the research subjects know they are receiving intervention or treatment, so they will do it seriously or earnestly, which can result in bias in curriculum evaluation research. In education, it is more complicated to standardize treatment. Other factors easily influence the influence of intervention in education, so the intervention's impact seems weak. (Norman Schmidt, G.R, H.G. 2000)

2. Research method

This research uses a phenomenological approach that relies on or understands the meaning behind the phenomena (noumena) described in detail. This research approach was developed from phenomenological philosophy (Phenomenological Philosophy), which is qualitative research. The purpose of the phenomenological study is to understand the respondents on the existence of everyone in society and describe the experience understood in interactions with others.

This research uses a phenomenological approach by describing an event or event that occurred at the Wahab Chasbullah Tambakberas Featured High School as it is, in this case, related to curriculum management innovation in realizing superior madrasah. Qualitative research produces analytical procedures that do not use statistical analysis procedures or other quantification methods. (Lexy J. Moleong, 2011). According to Creswell, "Qualitative research is a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research involves emerging questions and procedures, collecting data in the participants, setting, analyzing, the data inductively, building from particular to general themes, and making interpretations of the meaning of data. The final written report has a flexible writing structure."

Qualitative research means exploring and understanding the meaning of individual and group behavior describing social or human problems. The research process includes making research questions and procedures that are still temporary, collecting data in participant settings, analyzing data inductively, building partial data into themes, and then providing an interpretation of the meaning of the data. The last activity is to create a report with a flexible structure. For this reason, this researcher requires direct observation and involvement of researchers in dialogue with research sources. (Sugiono, 2016)

The type in terms of this research approach is qualitative, intending to explore some instances in depth by gathering sources of information. This study used a multi-site design, examining subjects with the same background and characteristics.

As the primary instrument (the key instrument), researchers can assess the situation and decide on something from the data collected or information obtained regarding madrasa-based management innovations in realizing superior madrasa. Finally, it can be described as the innovation of planning, implementing, and evaluating curriculum management in learning superior madrasa at the Superior MA Wahab Chasbullah Bahrul Ulum Tambakberas Jombang.

Researchers are planners, implementers, and data collectors and, ultimately, become reporters of research results. (Sugiono, 2016). In this qualitative research, the researcher's position becomes the critical instrument for understanding the meaning and interpretation of the phenomena occurring in schools, so the researcher's direct involvement with the research object is needed. (Sugiono, 2008)

The researcher's presence as the main instrument in research can introspect and assess whether his presence disturbs the respondent. If his presence disturbs, the researcher will be able to fix it. This is in line with the opinion put forward by Lexy J. Moleong that the position of a researcher in qualitative research is quite complicated. At the same time, he is a planner, executor of data collector, analyzer, interpreter, and, ultimately, a reporter for his research. (Lexy J. Moleong, 2011)

The data source in research is the subject from which the data can be obtained. (Suharsimi Arikunto, 2010). For this reason, the data obtained must come from the right data source. If correct, the data collected will be relevant to the studied problem. In this research, the data is in descriptive form, in the form of information or facts obtained through observation or analysis in the field, which can be analyzed to understand a phenomenon to support a theory.

Data analysis is the process of systematically searching and compiling data from interviews, field notes, and other materials so that it is easy to understand, and the findings can be informed to others. (Sugiono, 2016)

3. Discussion

The head of the madrasah carries out curriculum evaluation through various meetings and conferences. To assess and review the extent to which the madrasah program has been implemented. Discussions with the deputy head of the madrasah are held once a month, while with teachers, they are held twice a semester. Meanwhile, evaluation with the madrasah committee and with the parents of students is carried out twice a year, namely at the beginning of the *sannah* and receiving report cards. While the teacher's evaluation of students through observation, tests, and mentoring students who excel or have problems. Therefore, teachers have their innovations regarding the evaluation techniques used. Ultimately, every teacher has notes or track records of student development during learning.

This supports the theory of Gall and Borg, as cited by Ashiong P. Munthe, who said, "Educational evaluation is the process of making judgments about the merit, value, or worth of educational programs". (Ashiong P. Munthe, 2015). Educational evaluation is the process of judging educational programs' achievements, grades, or worth. Thus, curriculum management innovation at the Superior MA K.H. Abd. Wahab Chasbullah Bahrul 'Ulum Tambakberas Jombang, in terms of evaluation, also always pays attention to other parties who have an enormous contribution to the progress of madrasa, including the board of caregivers/leaders of Islamic boarding schools, madrasah committees and guardians of students, so that it appears that in terms of evaluating MAU-DU and MAU-WH curriculum management innovations also run well and get more value for madrasah residents.

In particular, the evaluation carried out at these two madrasas covered several areas, including teacher and student evaluations.

3.1. Evaluation of Educators and Education Personnel

In evaluating teachers, four main points must be conveyed below.

- In the administrative evaluation, a teacher must fill in the points specified in the state using a form.
- By using clinical supervision.
- By holding a review with the teachers at the end of the semester.
- Madrasah self-evaluation (EDM), which is individual.
- Student Evaluation

Based on the findings obtained by researchers regarding innovation, curriculum evaluation carried out on students is by observation, portfolio, and colleagues. There are daily tests, PTS (midterm assessment), PAS (end semester assessment), worship practices (prayer, *zakat*, pilgrimage rituals, the practice of caring for corpses, slaughtering sacrificial animals), practice exams for reading books, *munaqosah tahfiz* (direct assistance) by testing one's memorization of both hadith and Al-Qur'an memorization, then three language exams (TOEFL and TOAFL), there is a final assignment exam, namely students carry out research based on the integration of religious, scientific and social knowledge. Then, the students are deployed in the community for social service, becoming priests, preachers, and preachers. Meanwhile, if they do not pass, there is separate guidance carried out by a special team assigned by the head of the madrasa, after which a remedial program is carried out, and they are required to complete it thoroughly.

This follows Government Regulation Number 32 of 2013 concerning Structuring National Education standards. Several provisions regarding curriculum assessment/evaluation are stated as follows.

- Curriculum evaluation is an effort to collect and process information to increase the effectiveness of curriculum implementation at the national, regional and educational unit levels.
- The government, regional government, educational units, and the community evaluate the curriculum.
- The government carries out evaluations of national content and local content.
- Regional governments carry out local content evaluation under their respective authorities.

- The education unit conducts curriculum evaluation at the education unit level in coordination with the local Education Office.
- The community can evaluate national content, local content and educational unit-level curriculum.
- Curriculum evaluation is used to improve the curriculum.

The curriculum evaluation must follow the rules, which will later be able to provide changes to students. The curriculum evaluation process should be the responsibility of all elements in the education sector, both at the macro level (minister of education, director general of primary and secondary education, directors), *meso* level (Governor, Head of Provincial, District/City Education and Culture Office) and micro level (principal/madrasah, deputy principal/madrasah, supervisor, and teachers) in the school system. Therefore, education administrators are responsible for successfully implementing the established curriculum. It is necessary to develop an assessment program, which is a series of actions carried out within the framework of curriculum assessment as a management and evaluator tool in carrying out curriculum assessment.

The curriculum assessment program contains the following things. 1) Determination of the objectives of the assessment program. 2) Assessment of the assessment instrument. 3) Administrative assessment. 4) Data processing. 5) Analysis of interpretation. 6) Utilization of the results of the assessment. 7) Recording and reporting. The evaluation model that has been used is the CIPP evaluation model (context, input, process, product, and outcome). Context means evaluating the object, identifying weaknesses and strengths, diagnosing problems, providing solutions, and testing whether goals and priorities are adjusted to the needs to be implemented. Meanwhile, evaluating the input determines how the program objectives are achieved. This cannot be separated from human resources, facilities, supporting equipment, funds/budget, various necessary procedures, and rules.

The evaluation process is by checking the implementation of a plan/program. Product evaluation measures interpret and determines the achievement of the results of a program, ascertaining how much the program has met the needs of a group of programs served. Then, it is refined by using an outcome evaluation, which measures how much influence successful graduates have for the benefit of the life of the public and returning to serve the madrasa.

This also supports Stufflebeam's theory of the evaluation model, stating that "The CIPP approach is based on the view that the most important purpose of an evaluation is not to prove but to improve". The evaluation of the Stufflebeam model consists of four dimensions, namely context, input, process, and product, so the evaluation model is named CIPP. The four words mentioned in the CIPP abbreviation are evaluation targets, namely the components and methods of an activity program.

The advantages of MAU-DU and MAU-WH in implementing curriculum management innovations include that all components of the school have a high work ethic. This can be seen from the seriousness of the students in participating in the activities programmed by the madrasa, namely full-day school, extracurricular activities, and other activities as additional or supporting learning even though they feel tired. Among other high work ethics are as follows:

- There is a high commitment from madrasah residents to realize the vision, mission, and goals.
- Madrasahs have the competence to develop themselves under the work plan and madrasah income and expenditure budget (RAPBM).
- Good relationships with the School Committee, parents, community, and other institutions.
- The madrasah has achieved many achievements.

Many context evaluation formulations have been stated by evaluation experts, among them Sax. He explained that context evaluation is (G. Sax, 1980). The essence of the Stufflebeam & Shinkfield quote above is that context evaluation seeks to evaluate the object's status, identify weaknesses and strengths, diagnose problems and provide solutions, and test whether goals and priorities are adjusted to the needs to be implemented. (Madaus, Scriven, & Stufflebeam, 2014). Stufflebeam Shinkfield explained that the purpose of Product Evaluation is to measure, interpret, and determine the achievement of the results of a program, ascertaining how much the program has met the needs of the program group served. According to Sax, the function of evaluating results is to help make decisions related to the continuation, end and modification of the program, the results achieved, and what to do after the program runs. (G. Sax, 1980)

4. Conclusion

Based on the research focus, data exposure, single site analysis, the research findings, and the results of this study can be concluded as follows.

Curriculum Evaluation Innovation in Creating a Leading Madrasah in a Leading MA KH. Abdul Wahab Chasbullah Bahrul 'Ulum Tambakberas Jombang. In the evaluation aspect, the madrasah head does this through various meetings and conferences, even by direct field observation. Discussions with the deputy head of the madrasah and the director of the curriculum are held once a month. Meanwhile, with teachers, it is done twice in one semester. Meanwhile, evaluations with the madrasah committee and the student's parents are carried out at the end of the semester.

Suggestions

Suggestions that can be given regarding this research are as follows:

- Madrasa heads should strive to develop conducive madrasa innovation through unique strategies adapted to the internal and external conditions of the educational institution they lead.
- For future researchers, it would be better if they research the same problem but be more careful in looking for unique gaps so that they can produce work that can enrich previous findings.
- For readers in general, this research can provide an overview of strategies that can be implemented to develop the madrasah climate to support the smooth running of the educational process, ultimately leading to increasing the quality of education.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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